

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 8.1. Project Identity Set (logo, banner, roll-up, poster, brochure, public website)

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP8
Deliverable no. & title	D8.1. Project Identity Set (logo, banner, roll-up, poster, brochure, public website)
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Lead Beneficiary	AP (partner 6)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NPI, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - ULAVAL, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UAF/CFOS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – AP, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – CSIC-UTM, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – IOPAN, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – FMI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – DTU-AQUA
Due date	28.02.2018
Delivery date	13.07.2018

1. Abstract

D8.1 compiles the Project Identity Set, composed of a logotype, a banner, a roll-up, ppt template, a brochure, a poster and a public website. The logo and the website were created at the beginning of the Project and were already presented during the Kick-Off meeting in February 2018. As showed in this document, the logo is used in a variety platforms and documents, on materials to promote the dissemination of the Project identity and on a set of templates to ensure an efficient communication within and about the Project.

2. Project Identity Set

2.1. Logo

The main idea for the Project Identity was to design a logotype easy to reproduce and to recognize. Two versions have been produced, one in blue to use in light backgrounds and other in white to use in dark backgrounds.

2.2. Banner

A set of banners was designed to be used in different promotional materials, see examples below. Further examples available at the project website.

**Making the Arctic accessible
for excellent science**

2.3. Poster and roll-up

A poster and a roll-up has been created to illustrate the main activities and objectives of ARICE at different events.

Poster:

ARICE - Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium

Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science

Nicole Biebow¹, Verónica Willmott¹ & the ARICE Consortium
¹Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany

ARICE

www.arice.eu

Providing better capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean

Networking	Joint Research Activities
<p>Develop strategies to ensure the optimal use of existing polar research vessels at a European and international level, working towards an international Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium which shares and jointly funds operational ship time on the available research icebreakers.</p>	<p>To improve the research icebreakers' services by partnering with the maritime industry on a „ships and platforms of opportunity“ programme and by exploring into new key technologies that could lead to an improvement of ship-based and autonomous measurements in the Arctic Ocean. Arice will also implement virtual and remote access to data via an innovative 3D Virtual Icebreaker.</p>

Transnational access to a set of 6 international research icebreakers in the high Arctic

<p style="font-size: 0.8em;">CCGS Amundsen, CA</p>		
<p style="font-size: 0.8em;">IB Oden, SE</p>		

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Roll-up banner 210 x 85 cm:

ARICE

Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium

Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science

Providing better capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean

Networking

- Optimal use of existing polar research vessels
- Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium
- Which shares and jointly funds operational ship time

Joint Research Activities

- Partnering with the maritime industry
- Exploring into new key technologies
- Innovative 3D Virtual Icebreaker.

Transnational access to a set of 6 international research icebreakers in the high Arctic

<p>RV Sikuliaq, USA</p>	
<p>RSS Sir David Attenborough UK</p>	
<p>IB Oden, SE</p>	

www.arice.eu

2.4. Brochure

A threefold brochure with information on ARICE goals and objectives has been designed to promote the Project.

www.arice.eu

The consortium consists of 15 partners from 13 countries in Europe, USA and Canada. These partners have joined forces to improve the capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

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ARICE
 Arctic Research
 Icebreaker Consortium

ARICE - EU Horizon 2020
 Knowledge - infrastructure
 Duration: 01/2018 - 12/2021
 EU contribution: €6M

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ARICE

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 accessible for
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GOALS & OBJECTIVES

Providing better capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean

1. Networking

Develop strategies to ensure the **optimal use of existing polar research vessels** at a European and international level, working towards an **international Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium** which **shares and jointly funds operational ship time** on the available research icebreakers.

2. Joint Research Activities

To improve the research icebreakers' services by partnering with the maritime industry on a „**ships and platforms of opportunity**“ programme and by **exploring into new key technologies** that could lead to an improvement of ship-based and autonomous measurements in the Arctic Ocean. Arice will also implement virtual and remote access to data via an innovative **3D Virtual Icebreaker**.

3. Transnational access

ARICE will provide transnational access to four European and two international research icebreakers. Access is granted based on scientific excellence of the research proposals, which researchers need to submit during the application process. The participating icebreakers are:

- PRV Polarstern, Germany
- IB Oden, Sweden
- RV Kronprins Haakon, Norway
- RRS Sir David Attenborough, United Kingdom
- CCGS Amundsen, Canada
- RV Sikuliaq, United States of America

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Partners

2.5. Public website

A public website <http://www.arice.eu> was created and opened to the public at the time of the ARICE Kick off Meeting (7th of February 2018). This website accommodates information on the project, on the ship time application opportunities, and surveys and news launched by the project ARICE. It also features dedicated webpages on the ARICE Research Icebreakers.

The website also hosts a dedicated Intranet section which allows project partners reach relevant ARICE documents and templates (see D8.3 and 8.5). The website will be constantly amended and upgraded as needed as the project develops.

An international collaboration strategy for
meeting the needs of marine based
research in the Arctic

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Goals and Objectives

ARICE's overall aim is to provide Europe with better capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

ARICE aims at reaching this goal with the existing polar fleet by:

1) Networking:

ARICE will develop strategies to ensure the optimal use of the existing polar research vessels at a European and international level. The aim is to establish an International Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium which shares and jointly funds ship time for scientists on the available research icebreakers.

2) Transnational access:

ARICE will provide transnational access to four European and two international research icebreakers. Access is granted based on scientific excellence of the research proposals, which researchers need to submit during the application process. The participating icebreakers are:

- PRV Polarstern, Germany
- IB Oden, Sweden
- RV Kronprins Haakon, Norway
- RRS Sir David Attenborough, United Kingdom
- CCGS Amundsen, Canada
- RV Sikuliaq, United States of America

3) Joint research activities:

ARICE will improve the research icebreakers' services by working closely together with maritime industry on a so called "ships and platforms of opportunity" programme. Through this programme, commercial vessels operating in the Arctic Ocean will collect oceanic and atmospheric data on their cruises. At the same time, science and industry will work together to explore new technologies, which can improve ship-based and autonomous measurements in the Arctic Ocean. ARICE will also implement virtual and remote access of data via an innovative 3D Virtual Icebreaker, which will provide anyone with real-time information from the Arctic.

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ARICE Survey - Ship based observations in the Arctic

Details
Created: 31 May 2018

In the Arctic Ocean, the collection of environmental data is still very limited due to the difficulty in accessing ice-covered waters. However, there is an urgent need for more data. Enhanced data coverage would benefit both the science community and the Arctic marine industry. It would help to deepen the understanding of the wide range of processes behind the changes in the Arctic. This data is also needed for better weather and ice forecasting models and risk assessment studies, and thus a key to improved safety and sustainability of all the operations in the Arctic Ocean.

[Read more ...](#)

Breaking the Ice with International Research Mobility

Details
Created: 02 May 2018

ARICE has been featured in an article from RESEARCHconnect on International Research Mobility, "Breaking the Ice with International Research Mobility" presented at the EARMA Conference in Brussels, 16-18 April 2018 (<http://www.earmaconference.com/>).

[Read more ...](#)

The "ARICE - Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium" Kick-off meeting

Details
Created: 15 February 2018

The "ARICE - Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium" Kick-off meeting was held at the German Maritime Museum in Bremerhaven, 6th to 7th of February 2018 and brought together 45 participants, representing all fifteen partner institutions from Europe, Canada and the USA, as well as key cooperation partners. The two-day meeting allowed work package leads to give an overview of the tasks ahead and fostered constructive discussions to pave the way towards a fruitful collaboration across borders. The ARICE consortium thus emerged eager to join efforts towards providing researchers with improved access to Research Icebreakers.

[Read more ...](#)

Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science

Details
Created: 02 February 2018

ARICE kick-off press release

Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science

EU funds an Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium, which will provide researchers with improved access to research icebreakers.

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[Vessels](#) / [PRV Polarstern](#)

PRV Polarstern

Operator: AWI - Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (partner AWI)

Country: Germany

Vessel Type: Ice Going Multipurpose RV

Ice Class: 100 A5

Operational Area: Atlantic Ocean, Arctic and Antarctic Oceans

Endurance: 75 days

Scientist Berths: 55

Length: 118m

Features:

PRV Polarstern is a double-hulled icebreaker operational at temperatures as low as -50 °C. The ship is able to sail through 2 m thick ice with a speed of 5 knots, and it breaks ice up to 3 m thickness. The ship contains nine research laboratories for biological, geological, geophysical, glaciological, chemical, oceanographic and meteorological research. Additional laboratory containers may be stored on and below deck. Refrigerated rooms and aquaria permit the transport of samples and living marine fauna. Special sounding devices with depth ranges up to 10,000 meters and which can penetrate up to 150 meters into the sea floor are available for scientific investigations. Hydro-acoustic survey systems such as Hydrosweep, Parasound and fishery sounders can be continuously operated.

Modality of access under this proposal:

Full access to PRV Polarstern will be offered for a cruise in combination with the MOSAIC expedition to the central Arctic in winter.

Due to the special configuration of MOSAIC, the funding provided by ARICE is limited to a maximum of 6 participants per leg.

Multiple combinations for this access are possible, depending on leg duration:

- Up to 5-6 participants / 1 leg (single project)
- Up to 2 participants in 3 legs (in one or multiple projects)
- 1 participant / 4-5 legs (in one or multiple projects)

Applications are welcome for a minimum of 1 person/leg.

Potential applicants are warned that their work will span the full leg duration and that change of personnel can only occur between MOSAIC legs.

Applications must fit into the MOSAIC time schedule and work programme. Applicants to PRV Polarstern in the frame of MOSAIC will be required to submit, together with the ship-time application, an Endorsement Letter from MOSAIC (for more information, see the call documents) A special medical examination to prove the ability to work in this extreme environment is required to access PRV Polarstern for an Arctic cruise.

Support offered under this proposal:

- a. Transportation of cargo and personnel,
- b. Food and accommodation,
- c. Lab space and power supply,
- d. Communication,
- e. Operational and logistic supports,
- f. Basic data from meteorology, navigational and hydrographical observatories;
- g. Medical care.

Scientists accessing the RV through ARICE will be part of the MOSAIC winter experiment, sharing the PRV with other international cooperation.

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2.6. Project templates

The Project also created a set of templates to ensure an efficient communication within the Project and to create common working and reporting tools as well as presentation templates, ppt's for internal and external presentations.

The templates are available at the ARICE Intranet website section -(see D8.5).

2.6.1. Deliverable and milestone template (Word format)

2.6.2. Presentation template (PowerPoint)

Template for 4:3

Title of presentation

Date of presentation

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Arctic Research Icebreaker Cons.
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Header – text here

- Main text here or bullets

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Template for widescreen (16:9)

Title of presentation

Date of presentation

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- Main text here or bullets

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